

THE ROLE OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN SMALL BUSINESSES IN NEW UZBEKISTAN: ISSUES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ENHANCED EFFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT

In the conditions of New Uzbekistan, the system of vocational training is being constantly improved, taking into account the existing demand and needs for professional qualifications of employees in enterprises. In particular, “in our country, first of all, consistent efforts are being made to increase the welfare of the population, especially the youth, by creating new jobs and actively supporting entrepreneurship initiatives. At the same time, addressing the tasks in this area has led to the necessity of creating an effective system for training highly qualified specialists, taking into account the needs of the labor market, including the large enterprises and clusters being established in the regions

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According to the existing legislation in the country, increasing the level of vocational training of personnel is based on the development prospects and priority tasks of the economy, modern technical and technological trends, real demand for labor in the labor market, employers' proposals, and the principle of “lifelong learning,” and is evaluated as a professional education system. The professional education system prepares mid-level personnel, and its goal is to train competitive personnel for the labor market, including for small businesses and private entrepreneurship entities, through the introduction of professional education stages, as well as meeting the demand for lifelong learning of individuals of different ages.

¹ Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 394 “On measures to improve the system of training qualified personnel for professions in high demand in the labor market”, 13.05.2019. <https://lex.uz/docs/4334806>

At the same time, systematic reforms aimed at improving the system of professional education services for the population, training mid-level personnel, and ensuring their effective employment are being consistently implemented in the country. In particular, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 24, 2017, No. PF-5052, "On measures to further improve state policy in the field of employment and fundamentally increase the efficiency of labor bodies," the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population of the Republic of Uzbekistan was reorganized into the Ministry of Poverty Reduction and Employment.

Currently, the country's training programs aimed at increasing personnel potential are not fully aligned with the "International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED)" levels of the UNESCO organization, which hinders the full implementation of Uzbekistan's qualification system². Moreover, this has led to the situation where the professional qualifications of the personnel being trained in the education system do not sufficiently meet the requirements set by employers. This, in turn, negatively affects the effectiveness of the use of personnel potential in enterprises.

According to research conducted by the World Bank group on youth employment issues and their potential solutions, the population aged 29 and under in Uzbekistan is 18 million, which is the highest among other countries in Europe and Central Asia. According to the data, 26.4% of people aged 16-29 are not employed, not in education, or not enrolled in professional training courses. Among 15-24-year-olds, 5% are classified as "disengaged," and among 25-29-year-olds, this figure is 4%. In terms of the proportion of youth unable to find suitable employment and becoming "disengaged," Uzbekistan ranks higher compared to other Central Asian countries, where the average percentage is 2.5%.³

The working-age population in the country is expected to increase by 12% in the next decade, reaching its highest level by 2045. According to analyses, in 2020, around 535,000 youth graduated from vocational colleges and higher education institutions. Among the population aged 16 and older in Uzbekistan, about 5.5% are international labor migrants, with nearly 90% of them being male. The most significant receiving countries for Uzbek labor migrants are Russia, Kazakhstan, and Turkey, with the majority being in the 25-34 age group. Research by World Bank experts on youth employment issues shows that in rural areas, the main issues for youth employment include a lack of job opportunities, low demand for labor, high levels of informal employment, and low wages.

According to World Bank experts, issues such as insufficient demand for labor to involve new labor resources entering the labor market, lack of knowledge and skills, financial challenges, imperfect state employment programs, and social norms were identified as key problems in youth employment.

Furthermore, the country regularly implements training programs aimed at improving qualifications and retraining personnel to increase the effectiveness of using personnel

² Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to further improve the professional education system" No. PF-5812, 06.09.2019. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/4500926>

³ Honorati, Maddalena Marguerie, Alicia Charlena. Youth Employment in Uzbekistan: Opportunities and Challenges. Washington, D.C. : World Bank Group. September – 2021. p. 89. <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/235891634705237783/youth-employment-in-uzbekistan-opportunities-and-challenges>

potential. These programs focus on updating and deepening specialists' professional knowledge and skills. The qualification improvement and retraining procedure, and its frequency, can be independently determined by the relevant ministries, departments, organizations, and enterprises. Some sectors may have specific requirements for improving qualifications and retraining. Upon completing qualification improvement and retraining programs, individuals are awarded a certificate or diploma in the form approved by the state.

As President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev emphasized, "In the conditions of increasing global market competition, ensuring the economic development of the country through improving the quality of education and scientific potential, and enhancing the efficiency of the personnel training system is of paramount importance."⁴ For this reason, priority is being given to the implementation of education programs aimed at preparing mid-level personnel and highly educated specialists that meet the professional demands of enterprises in the conditions of New Uzbekistan. Additionally, in recent years, enterprises in various sectors of the national economy have been increasingly involved in training their employees, providing vocational training, and improving their qualifications. In our opinion, in the coming years, the strengthening of the integration between "education – science – production" will lead to positive changes in the indicators of using personnel potential effectively while increasing its quality.

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⁴ Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-62 "On measures to radically improve the system of personnel training for sectors of the economy", 07.02.2024. <https://lex.uz/docs/6794040>